

Antibiofilm Activity of Coconut (*Cocos Nucifera*) Leaflets Against Microorganisms Causing Nosocomial Infections

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Abstract. This study aimed to determine the antibiofilm activity of coconut leaflets on selected biofilm-forming bacteria and fungus. Coconut leaflets were extracted and processed to obtain crude extract using aqueous, ethanol, and methanol solvents. Minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) was determined to evaluate the effectiveness of the various solvents against *S. aureus*, *P. aeruginosa*, and *C. albicans*. After that, eradication assay was done by staining the wells with preformed biofilm using crystal violet and the visualization of both biofilm inhibition and eradication were observed under the microscope. Results show that among the three solvents, ethanolic extract of coconut leaflets with a 1:2 dilution concentration was found to effectively inhibit the biofilm of *S. aureus*, *P. aeruginosa*, and *C. albicans*, with a biofilm inhibition of 44%, 77%, and 50%, respectively. Results of the microscopic observation, based on the presence of bacterial cells, yeast cells, microcolonies, pseudohyphae/true hyphae, and reduction in the coverage of biofilm formed, shows that the biofilm inhibition activity of ethanolic extract of coconut leaflets with 1:2 dilution concentration was found to be significantly effective against all three microorganisms. With the same parameters, the biofilm eradication activity of ethanolic extract of coconut leaflets with a 1:2 dilution concentration was found to be lacking. These findings prove that the coconut leaflets have antibiofilm activity with 1:2 dilution concentration of ethanol as the solvent. This suggests its potential to be a biofilm inhibitor against nosocomial infection-causing microorganisms in the hospital setting.

Keywords: biofilm, biofilm eradication, biofilm formation, microcolonies, minimum inhibitory concentration

I. INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

Nosocomial infections are those acquired by patients during healthcare treatment, typically developing 48 hours after hospitalization (World Health Organization, 2024). These infections can cause severe complications such as sepsis and death. Haque et al. (2018) identify several contributing factors, including invasive procedures, use of medical devices, poor hygiene, and inadequate medical practices. HAIs not only extend hospital stays but can also spread to patients' relatives. Common types include urinary tract, respiratory, bloodstream, and surgical site infections. Raoofi et al. (2023) report a global HAI rate of 8.7%, with higher prevalence in the Eastern Mediterranean and lower in the Western Pacific. Rates range from about 5% in North America and parts of Europe to up to 40% in some regions of Asia, Latin America, and Africa, largely due to poor adherence to safety protocols.

Sikora and Zahra (2023) note that nosocomial infections are caused by various microbes, including bacteria, viruses, and fungi. Common gram-positive bacteria include coagulase-negative Staphylococci, Streptococcus, and Enterococcus species. Drug-resistant strains like MRSA, VISA, and VRSA are especially concerning. Fungal infections, particularly from *Candida* species, often affect immunocompromised patients or those with medical devices.

Sadly, financial constraints pose significant challenges in controlling HAI in countries like the Philippines, which is considered a developing country. Hence, there is a call to explore the natural approach in combating biofilm-forming microorganisms, which are a major cause of persistent infections in healthcare settings. By investigating the antibiofilm properties of coconut leaflets, this research contributes to the search for alternative solutions that could aid in lessening the nosocomial infection. In the laboratory, this study provides a basis for further investigation into plant-based antibiofilm agents, potentially leading to the development of new antibiofilm treatments. For the medical community, the findings could have practical applications in infection prevention and treatment.

The significance of this study lies in its investigation of the antibiofilm activity of coconut leaflets against nosocomial infection-causing microorganisms. These microorganisms pose significant health risks, particularly in immunocompromised individuals. Coconut leaflets, a readily available and natural resource, have shown promise in antimicrobial activity. Exploring their potential to inhibit and eradicate these microorganisms could lead to the development of novel, eco-friendly antibiofilm therapies.

Statement of the Objectives

This study aimed to determine the antibiofilm activity of coconut leaflets on selected biofilm-forming bacteria and fungus. This study was conducted from January to May 2025.

Specifically, this sought to achieve the following objectives.

1. To determine the most effective extracting solvent for an antibiofilm activity.
 - a. Aqueous
 - b. Ethanol
 - c. Methanol
2. To determine the most effective concentration based on the minimum inhibitory concentration of coconut leaflets crude extracts for each extracting solvent.
3. To evaluate the antibiofilm activity of coconut leaflets crude extracts against the following microorganisms in terms of:
 - a. Inhibition
 - b. Eradication

II. METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study utilized experimental design. The crude extract of coconut leaflets was prepared using different extracting solvents specifically aqueous, ethanol, and methanol. Minimum inhibitory concentration assay, biofilm inhibition assay, and biofilm eradication assay were performed to determine the most effective extracting solvent and concentration in the antibiofilm activity of coconut leaflets against nosocomial infection-causing microorganisms. Control groups were also utilized in this study. The positive control consisted of microorganisms grown in sterile growth medium without the addition of the extract, serving to confirm the ability of the microorganisms to form biofilm under the experimental conditions. The negative control consisted of sterile growth medium without microorganisms and without extract.

Study Site and Sample Collection

The study was done at the Center for Natural Sciences of Saint Mary's University (CNS-SMU), Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya. The coconut leaflets were collected at the Villaverde-Bagabag

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road of Bagabag, Nueva Vizcaya, as the location is abundant in coconut trees. *S. aureus*, *P. aeruginosa*, and *C. albicans* were obtained from Center for Natural Sciences of Saint Mary's University. Microtiter plate reading was performed at Nueva Vizcaya Provincial Hospital (NVPH) Laboratory located at Bambang, Nueva Vizcaya.

Plant Certification

Cocos nucifera leaves were submitted to the College of Forestry, Environment, and Resource Management of Nueva Vizcaya State University, Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya for certification for its taxonomic identity.

Data Gathering Procedure

Dried coconut leaflets were ground into a fine powder. For crude extraction, 500 g of the powdered material was soaked in 2 L of aqueous, ethanol, or methanol solvent. After stirring for 1 hour and standing undisturbed for 24 hours, the mixtures were vortexed for 5 minutes and centrifuged at 10,000 rpm to separate the solid residues. The resulting supernatants were filtered using Whatman No. 3 filter paper and concentrated through solvent evaporation under reduced pressure using a rotary evaporator. The crude extracts were stored at 4°C until further analysis. This procedure was adapted from Alam et al. (2020).

To determine the minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) of biofilm formation, microbial suspensions of bacteria and fungi were prepared in Mueller-Hinton Broth (MHB) and standardized using the McFarland turbidity method. A control group without extract served as the positive reference. The assay was carried out in 96-well microplates, where extract-treated cultures were incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. Following incubation, planktonic cells were removed, and wells were washed three times with phosphate-buffered saline (PBS, pH 7.4) to eliminate non-adherent cells. Plates were dried at room temperature for 24 hours, and 200 µL of 0.3% (w/v) crystal violet solution was added to each well and allowed to stain for 15 minutes. Excess dye was removed by washing with PBS, and the bound crystal violet was solubilized using 30% (v/v) glacial acetic acid. Optical density was measured at 570 nm using a microplate reader (Chamás et al., 2023). Biofilm inhibition was calculated using the following formula:

$$\text{Biofilm inhibition (\%)} = [(\text{Control OD} - \text{Treated OD}) / \text{Control OD}] \times 100$$

Biofilm-forming strains of *S. aureus*, *P. aeruginosa*, and *C. albicans* were standardized according to the McFarland standard and added to 96-well microtiter plates. The crude coconut leaflet extracts, at MIC levels, were applied to the wells. Plates were incubated at 37°C for 24 hours to allow biofilm formation. After incubation, each well was washed three times with PBS to remove non-adherent cells and dried for 24 hours. Biofilms were stained with 125 µL of 0.1% crystal violet solution for 30 minutes, rinsed with distilled water, and then resolubilized with 30% (v/v) glacial acetic acid (Chamás et al., 2023).

The inhibition of biofilm formation was assessed using light microscopy. The resolubilized contents of the wells were mounted on glass slides and covered with cover slips. Observations under 100x magnification focused on bacterial cells and microcolonies for *S. aureus* and *P. aeruginosa*, and yeast cells along with pseudohyphae or true hyphae for *C. albicans*, based on the criteria used by Chamás et al. (2023).

For the eradication assay, 50 µL of standardized bacterial and fungal suspensions were placed into microplate wells and incubated at 37°C for 24 hours to allow biofilm formation. Afterward, the medium and planktonic cells were removed, and the wells were washed with PBS three times. MIC concentrations of the coconut leaflet extract were added and incubated for another 24 hours. Planktonic cells were discarded, wells were washed with PBS, and the

remaining biofilm was stained with crystal violet and resolubilized using 30% glacial acetic acid (Chamás et al., 2023).

Visualization of biofilm eradication followed the same microscopy procedure. The stained and resolubilized samples were mounted and examined under a light microscope at 100x magnification. Evaluation criteria included bacterial microcolonies and cell structures for *S. aureus* and *P. aeruginosa*, and fungal elements such as yeast cells and hyphae for *C. albicans*, following the method of Chamás et al. (2023).

Ethical Considerations

The study was approved by Saint Mary's University Research Ethics Board (SMUREB) with address and contact information at 2nd Floor, Rev. John Van Bauwel Hall, SMU Main Campus, Ponce Street, Don Mariano Marcos, Bayombong, 3700 Nueva Vizcaya, Philippines (email: reb@smu.edu.ph; Cellphone No.: 09177053041).

Laboratory Safety

All laboratory procedures were scheduled and conducted under the supervision of the laboratory assistants at the Center for Natural Sciences (CNS). The prescribed personal protective equipment (PPE), including a laboratory gown, was worn throughout all laboratory activities. Laboratory masks, as well as surgical gloves, were utilized during the extraction of plant materials and the susceptibility assay and antibiofilm assay. Furthermore, the laboratory assistant operated the autoclave.

Waste Disposal

Waste materials from the study included culture media, microtiter plates with microorganisms and plant extracts, micropipette tips, Pasteur pipettes, Whatman filter paper, glass slides and coverslips, gloves, masks, and hair caps. Contaminated culture media and microtiter plates were sealed in secure bags and autoclaved at 121°C for at least 30 minutes, then cooled and disposed of in labeled biohazard bags. Micropipette tips and Pasteur pipettes were placed in designated bins, with those exposed to infectious agents autoclaved prior to disposal. Whatman filter paper was discarded immediately in hazardous waste bins. Glass slides and coverslips were disposed of in puncture-resistant containers marked with a biohazard symbol. Used PPE, including gloves, masks, and hair caps, was discarded in biohazard bins. Laboratory gowns were decontaminated by soaking in 10% bleach for at least 30 minutes, then washed and dried overnight.

All laboratory procedures and waste disposal were carried out under the supervision of CNS-SMU laboratory assistants, medical technologists in SMU, and medical technologists of NVPH. The results were validated by medical technologists.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Section 1. Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) of the Aqueous, Ethanolic, and Methanolic Extracts

Table 1

Mean Percentage of Biofilm Inhibition Against *Staphylococcus aureus* Using Aqueous, Ethanolic, and Methanolic Extracts of Coconut Leaflets

Mean Percentage of Biofilm Inhibition (%)			
Dilution concentration	Aqueous	Ethanol	Methanol
1:2	47.09	50.25	40.50
1:4	22.19	16.68	2.22
1:8	16.74	2.09	1.56
1:16	15.85	3.55	10.18
1:32	20.92	16.55	12.11
1:64	8.23	30.08	20.99
1:128	18.68	29.82	22.26
1:256	10.37	12.97	32.67

Table 1 summarizes the percentage of biofilm inhibition in *Candida albicans* wells treated with three different coconut leaflet extracts. Similar to the results for *Staphylococcus aureus*, the 1:2 dilution consistently showed the highest inhibition across all extract types. The ethanolic extract achieved the greatest mean inhibition (50%), followed by the aqueous (47%) and methanolic extracts (40%). This highlights the 1:2 dilution's efficacy, particularly for ethanol, in inhibiting *C. albicans* biofilm formation.

These results suggest ethanol is the most suitable solvent for biofilm inhibition assays targeting *S. aureus* and *C. albicans*, while methanol appears more effective for *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. This aligns with Duniq et al. (2020), who reported ethanol's efficiency in extracting antimicrobial compounds. Similarly, Bouali et al. (2024) highlighted the antimicrobial activity of methanol extracts from *Plantago major* against both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria.

Overall, ethanol-based extracts showed the highest inhibition for *S. aureus* and *C. albicans*, while methanol was most effective against *P. aeruginosa*, emphasizing the importance of solvent selection in biofilm inhibition studies.

Section 2. Optical Visualization of Biofilm Inhibition and Eradication of *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and *Candida albicans*

Table 2
Staphylococcus aureus, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and *Candida albicans* Under Microscope
 Subjected to Biofilm Inhibition by Ethanolic Extract of Coconut Leaflets

Visualized Biofilm Inhibition Under Microscope		
Microorganism	Slides	Parameters
<i>S. aureus</i>	Control 	Control Bacterial cells: Present Microcolony/clusters: Present
	Treated 	Treated Bacterial cells: Reduced Microcolony/clusters: Reduced Reduction in the coverage of biofilm formed: Evident
<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	Control 	Control Bacterial cells: Present Microcolony/clusters: Present
	Treated 	Treated Bacterial cells: Reduced Microcolony/clusters: Reduced Reduction in the coverage of biofilm formed: Evident
<i>C. albicans</i>	Control 	Control Yeast cells: Present Pseudohyphae/true hyphae: Present
	Treated 	Treated Yeast cells: Reduced Pseudohyphae/true hyphae: Absent Reduction in the coverage of biofilm formed: Evident

Table 2 presents the visualized biofilm inhibition activity of ethanolic extract of coconut leaflets with 1:2 dilution against the three microorganisms. Specifically, it presents the visualized control and treated wells of *S. aureus*, *P. aeruginosa*, and *C. albicans*. The photos were chosen from

the photos taken during the three trials of biofilm inhibition. The inhibition was evaluated by looking at the presence of major components of the biofilm, bacterial/yeast cells, microcolonies, and pseudohyphae/true hyphae, as noted by Gulati et al. (2016). Reduction in the coverage of biofilm formed is the direct comparison of the control and treated wells suggesting if there is biofilm inhibition happened.

MIC of ethanolic extract of coconut leaflets can inhibit the biofilm of nosocomial-causing microorganisms, specifically, *S. aureus*, *P. aeruginosa*, and *C. albicans*. The ethanolic extract of coconut leaflets successfully inhibited the biofilms of *S. aureus*, *P. aeruginosa*, and *C. albicans* as seen in table 2. With the evident reduction in the coverage of biofilm formed among all the tested microorganisms and decreased bacterial cells and microcolonies, this suggests the effective biofilm inhibitory capability of the ethanolic extract of coconut leaflets.

Table 3
Staphylococcus aureus, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and *Candida albicans* Under Microscope Subjected to Biofilm Eradication by Ethanolic Extract of Coconut Leaflets

Visualized Biofilm Inhibition Under Microscope		
Microorganism	Slides	Parameters
<i>S. aureus</i>	Control 	Control Bacterial cells: Present Microcolony/clusters: Present
	Treated 	Treated Bacterial cells: Present Microcolony/clusters: Present Reduction in the coverage of biofilm formed: Absent
<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	Control 	Control Bacterial cells: Present Microcolony/clusters: Present
	Treated 	Treated Bacterial cells: Present Microcolony/clusters: Present Reduction in the coverage of biofilm formed: Absent
<i>C. albicans</i>	Control 	Control Yeast cells: Present Pseudohyphae/true hyphae: Present
	Treated 	Treated Yeast cells: Present Pseudohyphae/true hyphae: Present Reduction in the coverage of biofilm formed: Absent

Table 3 presents the visualized biofilm eradication activity of ethanolic extract of coconut leaflets with 1:2 dilution against *S. aureus*, *P. aeruginosa*, and *C. albicans*. Bacterial cells and microcolonies were present in the visualized control and treated wells of *S. aureus* and *P.*

aeruginosa. There was no reduction in the coverage of biofilm formed, further indicating that there was no biofilm eradication that happened in the treated wells of *S. aureus* and *P. aeruginosa*. Yeast cells and pseudohyphae/true hyphae were present in the visualized control and treated wells of *C. albicans*. There was no reduction in the coverage of biofilm formed, further indicating that there was no biofilm eradication that happened in the treated well of *C. albicans*.

The result of the biofilm eradication using the microtiter plate assay and visualization using crystal violet is correlated with the study of Du et al. (2018). The study revealed that the concentration of epigallocatechin gallate (EGCG), a plant compound, was able to inhibit the biofilm formed by *Listeria monocytogenes* but could not eradicate its biofilm. According to Du et al. (2018), low concentrations of plant extract could inhibit biofilm formation, even if those concentrations were not bactericidal. According to Hall and Mah (2017), MIC is generally not enough to eradicate a mature biofilm. Even though MIC is effective to inhibit the biofilm during its initial stages of formation, it is not effective to eradicate the preformed biofilm.

Hence, while the ethanolic extract of coconut leaflets demonstrated effective biofilm inhibition during the early stages of microbial development, it could not eradicate established biofilms of *S. aureus*, *P. aeruginosa*, and *C. albicans*. In terms of inhibition, the ethanolic extract of coconut leaflets successfully inhibited all the selected microorganisms. While in biofilm eradication, the ethanolic extract of coconut leaflets showed no antibiofilm activity.

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

The study aimed to determine the antibiofilm activity of coconut leaflets on microorganisms causing nosocomial infection, namely, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and *Candida albicans*, using three different solvents, aqueous, ethanol, and methanol. The study confirmed that ethanol is the best solvent for coconut leaflets crude extract among all solvents tested. The 1:2 dilution of the ethanolic extract effectively inhibits the growth of these microorganisms and suggests its efficacy for biofilm inhibition. Although the coconut (*Cocos nucifera*) leaflet extract showed biofilm inhibition, complete biofilm eradication was not achieved at the tested concentration. This indicates that even though the ethanolic extract of coconut leaflets demonstrates biofilm inhibition, further optimization is required to maximize its efficacy in biofilm eradication. These findings prove that the coconut leaflets have antibiofilm activity with 1:2 dilution concentration of ethanol as the solvent. This suggests its potential to be a biofilm inhibitor against nosocomial infection-causing microorganisms in the hospital setting.

Recommendations

1. While the current study demonstrates in vitro antibiofilm potential, future research should explore the efficacy of the coconut leaflet extract in in vivo models to assess its performance within a biological system and to evaluate potential toxicity.
2. To further evaluate the effectiveness of solvents in extraction, it is recommended to apply a comparative research approach. This would involve comparing different solvents under controlled conditions to determine their relative efficiencies.
3. Future research could explore the efficacy of sequential treatments, starting with the coconut leaflet extract followed by conventional antimicrobials, to see if this approach enhances biofilm eradication.
4. Investigate whether the coconut leaflet extract can enhance the susceptibility of the tested pathogens within biofilms to conventional antibiotics, potentially helping to combat antibiotic resistance.

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